

ISic3026

I.Sicily inscription 3026

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory no inv.

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334105

1. [— κλώ]διος □ Ὀρέστας
2. [— Σ] ήλιος □ Βά,ρηξ
3. [άγο] ρανομήσαντες
4. [τὸ βή]μα □ θησαυροῦ.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645382

PHI 334105

Bibliography

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